

POPULATION DYNAMICS OF THE MUSTARD APHID AND ITS COCCINELLID PREDATORS

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ABSTRACT : Population dynamics of the mustard aphid and its coccinellid predators were studied in the Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture, SKRAU, Bikaner, during *rabi* 2013-14 & 2014-15. The incidence of mustard aphid, *Lipaphis erysimi* (kalt.) began in the first week of February 2014 & 2015 that gradually increased in numbers reaching to the maximum in the 9th & 8th SMW of 2014 & 2015 respectively. The aphid population was non – significant negatively correlated with maximum & minimum temperature and with mean relative humidity it was significant negative correlation. The predatory activity of the coccinellids, *C. septempunctata* also began in the first week of February and the adult of coccinellids had a significant positive correlation with aphid population.

Key words : Coccinellid predators, mustard aphid, population dynamics.

INTRODUCTION

Mustard, *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kalt.) commonly known to oilseed crop that belongs to family Apiaceae. Rajasthan contributes more than 70 percent of the total production of coriander in India. The area, production and productivity happens to be 29.27 lakh ha and production (37.64 lakh t) with productivity of 1286 kg per ha in Rajasthan (Anonymous, 2014). Among the insect-pests of mustard, the aphid, *L. erysimi* (L.) has been reported as a regular and major pest in Rajasthan and other parts of the country. The other pests include: sawfly (*Athalia lugens proxima*), aphid (*Lipaphis erysimi*), painted bug (*Bagrada cruciferarum* L.) and leaf miner (*Phytomyza horticola*). The most favorable temperature is 20°C or below. Cloudy and cold weather help in accelerating the growth of insects. Mustard aphid, *L. erysimi* is very devastating and the most destructive, reducing the crop yields considerably (Gupta *et al*, 2003). Ahuja (1990), Choudhury *et al* (2001), Gami *et al* (2002) and Singh and Lal (2012) who observed non significant negative correlation with maximum & minimum temperature and rainfall. Mandal & Patnaik (2006) and Ali *et al* (2012) who reported positive correlation between *C. septempunctata* and aphid population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was conducted at research farm, College of Agriculture, Bikaner (Raj.) during 2013-14 and 2014-15. The experimental plots were ploughed twice with desi plough and leveled with heavy plank 15 days before sowing the crop. Half of the recommended

dose of nitrogenous fertilizers and full dose of phosphate and potash fertilizers were applied at the time of last ploughing and the rest of the nitrogenous fertilizer was applied through top dressing during first irrigation and second irrigation. Sowing was done by manually operated hand driven plough keeping row to row distance of 30 cm with seed varieties of Laxmi. Five irrigations were applied at an interval of 25 days. First irrigation was applied at 25 days after sowing, second 45 days after sowing and remaining at 60 days, 75 days and 100 days after sowing. keeping the plant to plant distance at 10 cm. Other cultivation practices were followed as per recommendation and on a need basis. Data on weather factors, such as weekly minimum and maximum temperature, relative humidity and rainfall were obtained from the meteorological observatory of the ARS, Bikaner. The population of aphid obtained from experimental fields was subjected to statistical analysis (analysis of variance). The study on incidence of mustard aphid and its natural enemies were made on the crop sown in one plots each of 10 × 10 m². Ten plants were selected, tagged and observed early in the morning on 10 cm of terminal portion of the tagged plants for aphids and adult *C. septempunctata*. The prevailing atmospheric temperature and relative humidity and rainfall were recorded. The population data of the aphids as well as the natural enemies were correlated and Coefficient of correlation (r-value) was found-out between biotic & abiotic factors and population of the aphid.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The infestation of aphids started in the first week of February of 2013-14 and 2014-15. (aphids per plants) that gradually increased reaching to the maximum on 4th & 3rd week of February of 2013-14 and 2014-15 having 76.9 & 62.9 aphid per plant and 19.7 & 19.5 predators (tables 1 & 2). When the maximum & minimum atmospheric temperature was 25.9 & 11.3°C and 30 & 16.9 °C respectively and mean relative humidity was 55.46 & 56.10 per cent, respectively. The linear relationship between the aphid population and abiotic

factors of the environment showed a varied response. The coefficient of correlation (table 3) between aphids and maxi & minimum temperature ($r = -0.2329$ & -0.1256) of 2013-14 and ($r = -0.2732$ & -0.00218) of 2014-15 was non – significant negative; though in the case of RH ($r = -0.65059$ & -0.50367) of 2013-14 and 2014-15, the correlation coefficient was negative significant while rainfall ($r = 0.1431165$) had non significant positive correlated.

During the present study only two species of coccinellid predator's viz., *Coccinella septempunctata*

Table 1 : Population dynamics of aphid on mustard during rabi, 2013 - 2014.

Standard Meteorological weeks	Dates	Temperature (°C)		Av. relative humidity (%) (mm)	Total rainfall	<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> Population/plant	Aphid Population/ plant
		Maximum	Minimum				
6	7.02.14	23	9.2	47.30	0	0.00	9.4
7	14.02.14	23.2	8.4	49.75	0	4.61	16.2
8	21.02.14	26	9.1	46.95	0	9.61	35.5
9	28.02.14	25.9	11.3	46.00	0	19.7	76.9
10	7.03.14	27.8	14.6	44.60	0	5.73	29.7
11	14.03.14	30.1	11.4	54.35	0	4.21	12.3
12	21.03.14	32.7	16.4	60.35	0	0.89	4.6
Correlation		-0.23299	-0.12561	-0.65059		0.9813	

Table 2 : Population dynamics of aphid on mustard during rabi, 2014-2015.

Standard Meteorological weeks	Dates	Temperature (°C)		Av. relative humidity (%) (mm)	Total rainfall	<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i> Population/plant	Aphid Population/ plant
		Maximum	Minimum				
6	4.02.2015	25.3	7.3	52.20	0.0	1.2	12.8
7	11.02.2015	29.9	11.4	50.35	0.0	12.5	24.7
8	18.02.2015	30	16.9	56.10	0.0	19.5	62.9
9	25.02.2015	24	9.7	46.45	38.1	14.5	47.8
10	4.03.2015	23.9	11.4	53.20	11.3	11.4	29.2
11	11.03.2015	26.5	14.1	58.75	17.3	7.3	12.6
12	18.03.2015	36.1	19	67.30	0	1.8	3.9
Correlation		-0.27316	-0.00218	-0.50367	0.28623	0.9258	

Table 3 : Correlation coefficients (r) between mustard aphid, weather parameters and *C. septempunctata*.

Abiotic components		Mustard aphid		
		2013-2014	2014-2015	Pooled
Temperature (°C)				
A	Maximum	-0.23299	-0.27316	-0.253075
B	Minimum	-0.12561	-0.00218	-0.063895
Average		-0.1793	-0.13767	
Average Relative humidity		-0.65059	-0.50367	-0.57713
Rainfall (mm)		-	0.286233	0.1431165
<i>Coccinella septempunctata</i>		0.9813	0.9258	0.9536

Linnaeus. and *M. sexmaculata* were recorded feeding on the mustard aphid. Of these *M. sexmaculata* was not recorded; later, *C. septempunctata* dominated. The coccinellid foraging on aphids began in the second (4.6 predator/plant) & first (1.2 predators/plant) week of February of 2013-14 & 2014-15 respectively and significant positive correlation ($r = 0.9813$ & 0.925) observed between aphid population, *L. erysimi* and predators during 2013-14 and 2014-15 respectively. Singh and Lal (2012) who observed non significant negative correlation with maximum & minimum temperature. The coefficient of correlation between aphids and maxi & minimum temperature was non-significant negative observed in the present finding. Ali *et al* (2012) who reported positive correlation between *C. septempunctata* and aphid population same also observed in the present investigation. Earlier, Singh (1982) and Mishra (1999) reported the temperature range from 20 to 25°C to be most favourable for the multiplication of aphids (*Rhopalosiphum maidis* and *L. erysimi*). During the present study, the observations indicated that with an increase in aphid population there was a slight increase in predator population, following the density-dependent pattern. However, as aphids multiply parthenogenetically, significant reduction in aphid population could not be seen. Our findings conform to the reports by Meena *et al* (2009), who worked on *Hyadaphis coriandari* (Das.) infesting coriander crop.

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